

LEVEL OF ABUSE AMONG UNIVERSITY FEMALE STUDENTS IN IRBID NATIONAL UNIVERSITY - JORDAN

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Abstract

The aim of this study is to identify the level of abuse experienced by female university students in Jordan, and to reveal the differences between the degrees of female students in colleges, the GPA and the academic years. The study sample consisted of (918) university students. The results of the study showed that the sample obtained an average degree of abuse, and that the most source of abuse is the university student, while transportation was the most places where university students are subjected to abuse. The results also indicated that there are statistically significant differences attributed to the variable of the faculties in terms of abuse for the benefit of humanities faculties, and that there are no differences in the degrees of female students for the abuse due to the variable of the GPA. Finally, the results indicated that there are statistically significant differences attributed to the variable of the academic years in favor of the second and third year students.

Keywords: Abuse, Irbid National University Female Students.

1. INTRODUCTION

Jordan is one of the countries where university education is prevalent. University includes tens of thousands of students of different age, specialization, level of education, place of residence, social status, economic and ethnic status, from adolescence to adulthood. As a result of differences between large numbers of students may occurs differences in views leading to the possibility of problems between students, and these problems may be psychological, moral, religious, social, emotional, sexual, health, political or behavioural abnormalities.

The universities in Jordan, like other universities in the world, where abuses are widespread, but of a different size and level, depending on different civilizational and cultural systems, and stages of historical development. This makes abuse a different and complex issue because of the circumstances of societies. The universities aim to achieve a set of objectives, including: Developing leadership cadres in various fields and gaining skills to develop the intellectual and mental abilities that qualify students to lead the movement of thought, culture and innovation in society, prepare specialists and encourage the field of scientific research, and strive to achieve social and cultural normalization of students, Which leads to the integration of their personalities and the growth of their awareness, self-integration and contribute to rebuild civilization positively (Shatnawi and Ababneh, 2007).

According to Coker, Sanderson, Cantu, Huerta & Fadden, 2008, Coker, Sanderson, Canto, Huerta & Fadden need to pay attention to the youth, especially the age group (15-25), because it is an important period in their lives, where their career and educational future is determined in this period. They noted that female students suffer as a result of being subjected to sexual, physical and psychological abuse and violence that is spreading within universities.

Definitions of abuse are numerous and can be defined as ill-treatment or neglect inflicting on the individual and causing non-accidental and unexplainable injuries or wounds (Ndasauka & Kayange, 2019). Or physical force that causes harm to a person, begins with humiliation and ends with physical abuse, and considers its practice unlawful (Al-Borai, 2002). The US National Center defined it as physical or mental injury, sexual abuse, or negligence of a person responsible for his or her care under conditions that threaten or harm a person's health and happiness (Nelson, Ojebuyi & Salawu, 2017).

It is also a variety of behaviors of physical, sexual, verbal, or psychological abuse, and is practiced by one party to force another party to do or abstain from certain behaviors, or is sexual abuse or neglect, or emotional abuse of the other party (Hasan, 2017). According to Matlin (2000), abuse of women involves intentional behavioral patterns that lead to harm, which may be psychological or social.

there are many types and forms of abuse, some of them believe that consists of verbal or emotional abuse under one name, physical, sexual, social, health, psychological and other, but the current study focuses on three types of abuse are: (verbal or emotional abuse, physical or physical abuse, and sexual abuse). It is one of the most abuses that female students are exposed in the university (Arditti, 2015).

The Manual of Statistical Diagnosis of Mental Illness (DMS.IV) indicates that verbal abuse is in the form of obscene words in front of others, disrespect and appreciation, cynicism and screaming in front of others (Banat, 2005), and the analytical penal dictionary has defined it as insulting and cursing whether by expressing the word. It may be used to deny the person's reputation or to damage his reputation (Shalala, 2004). It was also defined by the triangular legal dictionary, as insulting and degrading expression of contempt, and in the form of screaming or threat in a public or private place with the intention of libel and insult (Baalbaki, Nakhleh and Egypt, 2002).

Physical abuse is a form of abuse against female students on campus. The World Health Organization (WHO) has defined physical abuse as violent behavior such as slapping, throwing objects, pushing, kicking, dragging, burning, threatening weapons or using weapons. It also means the use of physical force against the victim, which may be done using hands, legs or any other tool, and is punishable by law, such as beating, biting, slapping, pushing, burning, pulling hair, pulling the ground, or Strangulation, or Threat of Weapons and Murder (Hankivsky, 2011; Awawdeh 2002; Al-Rifai 2007; Sharifin 2008). Crosson-Tower (2002) defined physical abuse as injuries caused by an active act, not as a result of accidents such as bruising, cuts, bruises, fractures or burns.

Crosson-Tower (2002) argues that sexual abuse is sexual exploitation and the satisfaction of adult sexual instincts through direct assault, intimidation or play. Dennis (2011) defined sexual abuse as an undesirable sexual experience, ranging from foreplay to sexual intercourse, by an older person. Winton & Mara (2001) defined sexual abuse as sexual friction and interaction, for sexual arousal on the part of the aggressor, and that the aggressor is in a position of power or authority, and can control the victim.

Manifestations of sexual abuse include behavioral disorders such as fear, constant tension, guilt, threats, contempt, and humiliation (Jackson, 2013). Borges, Banyard, & Moynihan (2008) suggest that, in order to reduce the prevalence of sexual abuse, universities should put in place preventive laws, policies, educational programs and comprehensive measures to determine sexual abuse at the university in order to educate students about the dangers of abuse.

Psychological effects are most prevalent among victims of abuse, as university female students are subjected to abuse, which may be fearful and surrender, and failure to report abusers (Cattaneo, DeLoveh & Zweig, 2008). In addition to their impaired mood, anger, depression, and suicide, as a result of public harassment the victim may be depressed, chronic health problems, and physical problems (Humphreys & Lee, 2009).

Abuse also has psychological and negative effects on the victim, as well as physical and health effects. Arnold, Gelaye, Goshu, Berhane & Williams, 2008 (Arnold, Gelaye, Goshu, Berhane & Williams, 2008) argue that there are some adverse health effects on female students at the university as a result of violence and abuse, such as smoking, drug and alcohol use, high blood pressure, obesity, and venereal disease (such as AIDS). This is confirmed by Vivancos, Abubaker and Hunter (Vivancos, Abubaker & Hunter, 2008), where they pointed out that the most common sexually transmitted diseases among students in universities in the UK (AIDS) (9.6%), in addition to the incidence of gastrointestinal disorders, especially abdominal pain, as a result of exposure To physical and sexual abuse (Arditti, 2015). Physical effects of violence and abuse include fractures, bruises, and physiological damage associated with physiology (Family Health Care Institute, 2009).

There are economic effects in addition to psychological, physical and health effects, which are a burden on society, university and family. McMahon (2008) argues that every sexual abuse on campus is paid by the victim for financial and health care costs and that the university handles some financial costs and helps to eliminate psychological and emotional trauma by providing basic medical services. The victim is a burden on society in terms of disrupting production or increasing the use of social services, as well as the costs of health treatment, testing, sampling, the burden of expenditure required by care and protection centers, and the costs of counsel (National Council for Family Affairs, 2005).

2. PREVIOUS STUDIES

Chandraratne, Fernando & Gunawardena (2018) conducted a study aimed at investigating the prevalence of physical, sexual and emotional abuse among a sample of Sri Lankan female university students. The sample consisted of (1500) female students. The results of the study

showed that physical abuse (45.4%), nationality (9.1%) and emotional (27.9%); while the percentage of students who suffered severe abuse as follows: physical abuse (0.3%), sexual (4.05%), and emotional (8.8%).

Spencer, Haffejee, Candy & Kaseke, 2016 conducted a study to investigate the prevalence of abuse among female university students in South Africa. The study sample consisted of (1354) students. The results of the study showed that (42.6%) of the sample were exposed to one type of abuse, emotional abuse was reported by (54.9%), physical abuse (20%), sexual abuse (8.9%), and (6.5%) were exposed for emotional, physical and sexual abuse.

hilbert, Josho, Jake, Williams, and Burhan's study (Philpart, M., Goshu, M. Gekaye, B., Williams, M. & Berhane, Y, 2009) indicates the prevalence and factors of abuse and violence at the University of Awassa in Ethiopia. A sample of (1378) male students and their level of violence and abuse against female students. The results of the study indicated that (24.4%) of the students practiced violence during the academic year (2008-2009) and that (15.8%) of the students practiced physical abuse, including: slapping (5.1%), payment (9.5%), and beatings Punching (8.3%), suffocation (6.1%), and the threat of weapons (10.1%). Sexual violence was (16.9%) and included: (12.9%) unwanted touch, (6.4%) attempted rape, and (3.2%) rape.

Juma (2009) conducted a study aimed at detecting the types of abuse faced by female university students and ways to address them. The sample of the study consisted of (1286) students. The results showed that the most common types of abuse are verbal abuse, followed by sexual abuse, and finally physical abuse. The most interesting source of excitement is the student. The results also indicated that transportation is one of the places where abuse occurs. Finally, the results indicated that there are no differences due to the impact of the college variable on all types of abuse.

Ferns & Meerabeau's study (2008) aimed to investigate the prevalence of verbal abuse experienced by nursing students. At the University of England, where the study sample consisted of (114) students from the third year students majoring in nursing. The results indicated that (45.1%) of the sample had experienced verbal abuse, (34.5%) were verbally abused, and (65.5%) saw other students exposed to verbal abuse. The study also found that there were other abuses against them such as insults, ill-treatment and sexual contact.

Peter, Kayleen & Laura (2008), in a study on female sexual abuse at the University of South Texas, and the risk of alcohol on a sample of (313) female university students, said that about (16) female students complained of being forced to practice Sex by university students, and about (149) female students denied any pressure on them to have sex, by university students.

Olley, (2008) examined the experiences of sexual abuse of children and adolescents in Nigeria through the dissemination of sexual awareness through the media. The sample consisted of (1079) male students (211) female students and (22) socially disadvantaged students in public secondary schools, where the researcher used a questionnaire to collect data on sexuality and current experiences. The results indicated that child sexual abuse is a serious factor for Sexual behavior among adolescents and socially disadvantaged in Nigeria, where (55%) of respondents said they had seen space stations that posed dangerous sexual behavior among

adolescents, so (24.6%) of adolescents became sexually active.

The Kenny & McEachern study (2007) aimed to find out the history of the family environment and its role in the vulnerability of USU female students to sexual abuse. The sample of the study consisted of (18) Hispanic female students who complained of sexual abuse on campus. The data were collected through individual interviews with students and their families, knowledge of cultural values and family relations. Qualitative data revealed the existence of family conflicts and poor skills in resolving these conflicts within families, increasing the vulnerability of female university students to sexual abuse from others.

Harter, Erbes & Hart (2004) conducted a comparative study in the UK to determine the character composition of female students who were sexually abused in childhood, and students who were sexually abused at university. The sample of the study consisted of (372) female students. The results indicated that the personalities of the students who were subjected to sexual abuse were characterized by a set of features such as: calm, peace, relaxation, ethical and religious standards, and they used preventive expressions that refer to freedom and care. The study found that the history of sexual abuse was associated with increased symptoms of stress and fewer expressions of emotional feelings.

Bronner et al. (2003) aimed at investigating the level of sexual abuse among nurses. The study sample consisted of (281) female nurses and (206) female nursing students. The results of the study showed that there is a decrease in the process of sexual abuse, and that (90%) of exposure to at least one type of sexual abuse, and that (30%) of them were not less than (4) times of abuse, and the results indicated that there are significant differences between Nurses and nursing students in the types of severe abuse (33%) for female nurses and (23%) for female nursing students, and that (26%) of the sample were exposed to types of severe abuse.

Shook, Gerrity, Jurich & Segrist (2000) aimed to detect violence caused by courtship among students in a sample of (572) university students, of whom (395) were female students and (177) from Students, who have affair. The results indicated that (82%) of the total sample admitted that they engaged in verbal aggressive behavior during the date of the meeting between them, and that (21%) of the respondents admitted that they carried out aggressive physical behavior. The results also showed that both sexes learned aggression by modeling the behavior of their parents when they were children.

The place of the current study from previous studies:

- 1 This study is characterized by being one of the first studies in the field of abuse (verbal, physical, and sexual) to which female students are exposed in private universities, where this study was conducted on female students at Irbid National University.
- 2 Many of the previous studies dealt with one type of abuse such as sexual, verbal, or physical abuse, but did not try to look at the types of verbal, physical and sexual abuse together, and this distinguishes this study from other studies.

Problem and questions of the study

The abuse of female students in universities has become a concern for university and even community workers. University students live in a sensitive and important period, where some studies pointed to the high level of abuse of female students at this university level in the study (Olley, 2008) ranged between (4) (24%) In Sri Lanka, the rate of physical abuse (45%) and sexual (1) (9.9%) and emotional (27.9%) (Chandraratne, etal, 2018).

The psychological aspect is an important factor in building the individual and society. The female student cannot be an active member in her family, university, or society, and the abuse of female students has become more noticeable in the environment of Arab universities (Majali, 2009). Through their work as faculty members and as specialists in psychological and educational counseling, the researchers found that many female students complain about the actions of the students. It is somewhat aggravated and is now facing not only the university community, but society as a whole, as a result of cultural differences and customs in Jordanian society, which affects the lives of female students, and may cause them anxiety, fear and panic of the abuser. Accordingly, the problem of the study arose to identify the level of abuse among a sample of female university students in Jordan, and by answering the following questions:

1. What is the level of abuse experienced by female university students?
2. What are the sources of abuse among female university students?
3. What are the places where abuse occurs?
4. Are there any statistically significant differences in the level of abuse attributed to the college variable (scientific, humanitarian) among female university students?
5. Are there any statistically significant differences in the level of abuse due to the GPA variable among female university students?
6. Are there any statistically significant differences in the level of abuse attributed to the variable of the academic year among female university students?

Importance of the study

The importance of the current study is highlighted by the role of psychological studies in the service of society, and the concerns directed to the study of female university students who are mothers of the near future, it must be enjoying mental health to qualify them to learn and acquire the skills necessary to perform their roles to the fullest. The theoretical importance of the study is that it contributes to detecting the level of abuse of female students in universities and their sources, and provide useful scientific information for those who formulate higher education plans about the abuse of female university students, and the associated behavioral and environmental problems that need to be studied and solutions, and to identify the size and sources of the phenomenon, and factors And the associated causes and effects, in order to assist in the development of effective educational extension programs to reduce this phenomenon. The importance of the study arises to shed the light on the abuse suffered by students at Irbid National University in Jordan in particular, and Arab universities in general. The practical

importance is to try to draw workers in universities and families to the disadvantages of abuse of female students, and its impact on the university and family life of female students, developing programs that reduce the level of abuse in order to improve the level of society and universities in Jordan. It can also benefit from the results through the development of plans for psychological counseling services necessary, to address the negative effects of abuse, and help students to adapt to positive, effective and proper.

Aims of the study

This study aimed to detect the types of abuse experienced by female university students; their sources and places of occurrence; and to reveal the differences between the degrees of female students in the faculties of science and humanity, GPA, and the academic years.

Limitations of the study

- **Human Limitations:** The present study was limited to female undergraduate students at Irbid National University and did not include male students.
- **Time limits:** the current study was limited to the students of the second semester of the academic year 2018/2019.
- **Spatial limits:** The current study was conducted at Irbid National University in Irbid, northern Jordan.
- **Objective limits:** The objective limits of the study are limited to the level of abuse of a sample of female university students at Irbid Private University in the light of some variables.
- The instrument used (the scale of abuse) and its psychometric properties.
- The implications of the concepts and terminology contained in the study are limited to the procedural and conceptual definitions specified therein.

Terminology of study

Abuse: Any act that intentionally harms or injures any other person, including inadequate assault in an unconscious manner, including: physical, verbal, sexual and other abuse (Fineman & Mykitiuk, 2009). It is procedurally known as the degree to which the respondent on the scale of abuse.

Physical abuse: An intentional act that causes injury or trauma to another person through physical contact (Giardino, Lyu & Giardino, 2019). The researchers define them as undesirable behaviors, which did not occur by chance, such as violent pushing, beating, throwing tools, and others which lead to physical harm to the injured students, and procedurally knows the degree to which the respondent on the scale of abuse.

Verbal abuse: is the negative exposure of the victim in a verbal manner to unethical words with the aim of victimization (Evans, 2010). The researchers define them as undesirable behaviors, which did not occur by chance, such as contempt and verbal insult, neglect, sharp looks, and ridicule of university students and procedurally knows the degree of respondent on

the scale of abuse.

Sexual abuse: is usually undesirable by one individual over another through sexual contact (Maniglio, 2009). The researchers define them as undesirable behaviors that did not occur by chance, aimed at satisfying sexual instincts intimidation and not by intimidation and procedurally known to the extent that the respondent on the scale of abuse.

3. METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

The present study followed the descriptive approach in one of its analytical forms, as it tried to detect the level of abuse experienced by female university students of all types.

Population of the study

The study population consisted of all undergraduate female students at Irbid National University, where they numbered (1230) female students.

Sample of the study

The study sample consisted of (918) students from different academic years, randomly selected. Table (1) shows the distribution of sample among the study variables.

Table 1: Distribution of the study sample according to independent variables

Variable	Levels	No.	%
GPA	Less than 67.9%	187	20.4%
	%75.9 – 68	341	37.1%
	% 83.9 – 76	258	28.1%
	84 and more	132	14.4%
Facility	Scientific	334	36.4%
	Humanity	584	63.6%
Academic year	First	227	24.7%
	second	219	23.9%
	Third	238	25.9%
	Fourth	234	25.5%
Total	-----	918	100%

Tool of the study

The researchers referred to the literature and previous studies related to the subject of abuse as a Jumah study (2009), and the Obada and Abu Doh (2007), and Khattnath (2007), and return (2002). The researchers felt that it is better to use the scale used in the Jumah study (2009).

Reliability

Juma (2009) validated the content of the scale of abuse by presenting it to seven (7) arbitrators with experience and competence of faculty members at Yarmouk University. On the basis of the arbitrators' suggestions, some items were amended, some items were added, and some inappropriate paragraphs were deleted.

In the current study, the researchers verified the indicators of the validity of the content of the scale, where it was presented preliminary to (9) arbitrators specialized in the field of measurement and evaluation, and counseling and educational psychology, and the Arabic language at Yarmouk and Irbid National universities, e they were asked to give an opinion. In the items of the scale in terms of language and clarity of meaning, in addition to any amendments and observations they deem appropriate, and in the light of the arbitrators' comments and opinions, some language has been modified and the items of the scale are maintained as they are, where the arbitrators were unanimous by more than (85%). The scale consisted of (33) itemss and the arbitrators pointed out the suitability of the scale to the Jordanian environment.

The researchers also investigated to establish validity indicators for the scale of abuse by applying it to a sample of (53) female students from Irbid National University from outside the study sample and from within its community, and using Pearson correlation coefficient, the values of item correlation coefficients were calculated by dimensions. As shown in Table (2).

Table 2: Corrected correlation coefficients for abuse scale paragraphs

Item No.	Verbal abuse	Item No.	Physical abuse	Item No.	Sexual abuse	Item No.	Places of abuse	Item No.	Source of Abuse
1	0.63	1	0.59	1	0.93	1	0.77	1	0.55
2	0.85	2	0.68	2	0.79	2	0.72	2	0.74
3	0.60	3	0.88	3	0.84	3	0.86	3	0.66
4	0.77	4	0.61	4	0.62	4	0.58	4	0.81
5	0.69	5	0.90			5	0.79	5	0.93
		6	0.83			6	0.67	6	0.75
		7	0.71			7	0.71	7	0.83
		8	0.82					8	0.59
		9	0.68						

It is noted from Table (2) that the correlated correlation coefficients for the scale as a whole ranged between (0.55 - 0.93), while the dimensions were as follows (0.63 - 0.85) for verbal abuse, (0.59 - 0.90) for physical abuse, and (0.62 - 0.93) For sexual abuse, (0.58 - 0.86) for the places of abuse, and (0.55 - 0.93) for the source of abuse, indicating that the tool has an acceptable degree of reliability.

Validity

Juma (2009) performed the validity of the tool by applying it to a survey sample of (77) female university students. The coefficient of internal consistency (Cronbach Alpha), which ranged between (0.72-0.85) for the fields, was extracted, while the coefficient for the tool as a whole was (0.90).

In the current study, the researchers applied the scale in its initial form to a survey sample from outside the study sample and from within its community, consisting of (53) female students. For two weeks from the first application, using the Pearson correlation coefficient, the coefficient of stability of the scale as a whole was (0.81). Table (3) shows the stability of each dimension of the scale separately.

Table 3: internal consistency coefficient (Alpha Cronbach) for each fields of the study tool and for the instrument as a whole

Field No.	Field	Items No.	Internal consistency	validity
1	Verbal abuse	5	0.83	0.85
2	Physical abuse	9	0.76	0.79
3	Sexual abuse	4	0.87	0.89
4	Places of abuse	7	0.69	0.74
5	Source of abuse	8	0.73	0.77
	Tool as a whole	33	0.78	0.81

Correct scale

The scale consists of (33) items, classified according to a five-point scale (5 = Strongly Disagree, 4 = Disagree, 3 = Neutral, 2 = Agree, 1 = Strongly Agree), based on the statistical standard it adopted by (Odeh, 1998) the total scale ranged between (33-165) degrees. The level of abuse is determined by the average degree on each of the three dimensions and on the overall scale as follows: A degree of (1.00–2.33) indicates a low level of abuse, a degree of (2.34–3.67) indicates an average level of abuse, and a degree of (3.68–5.00) refers to a high level of abuse (Odeh, 1998).

Statistical processing

The researchers used the statistical program of psychosocial sciences (SPSS) using the following statistical equations: Extraction of averages and standard deviations of the degree of the sample on the scale of abuse as a whole and its dimensions. In addition, the Kruskal-Wallis Test was used to determine the differences in the GPA, the ANOVA, and the Tukey Post Hoc Test for post comparisons to determine differences in the school year.

Procedures of the study

The study scale was prepared in its final form after verifying the validity and consistency indicators by presenting it to a group of specialized arbitrators, in addition to applying it to a survey sample from outside the study sample and from within its community, and extracting the values of the factors of validity and reliability. The total population of the study population was determined, and the sample of the study sample was selected randomly. The researchers themselves distributed the scale to the students inside the classrooms, and clarified the instructions related to the scale, and at the beginning, the researchers gave the students a general idea of the objectives of the study and its importance. They assured them that their participation was voluntary. The statements to be made will be treated confidentially. They should not rush to answer. The study tools were then collected after responding to all items, and after confirming the information, and answering all items, were prepared for the purposes of statistical analysis and data entry for computer memory, and then use the appropriate statistical processors, according to the program (SPSS) to answer the questions of the study, and draw conclusions.

Variables of the study

The study included the following variables:

Independent variables: Types of abuse: It has three levels: verbal abuse, physical, and sexual.

Intermediate variables:

1. facility: It has two levels: humane and scientific.
2. GPA has four levels: (less than 67.9), (68-75.9), (76-83.9) and (84 and above).
3. Academic year: It has four levels are: (first year, and a second year, and third, and fourth).

Dependent Variables: Level of abuse among students of Irbid National University.

4. RESULTS OF THE STUDY

Results The questions the study tried to answer.

Question 1: What is the level of abuse of female students of Irbid National University?

To answer this question were calculated averages and standard deviations of the responses of female university students on each Field of the study tool and the tool as a whole and related to the type of abuse suffered by female students. As shown in Table (4).

Table 4: Means and standard deviations of the responses of university students on each area of the study tool and on the tool as a whole and related to the type of abuse to which they were subjected in descending order according to the mean

Item No.	Field	Rank	Mean*	Standard deviation	Level
1	Verbal abuse	1	3.92	0.78	High
3	Physical abuse	2	3.61	0.95	Medium
2	Sexual abuse	3	3.46	0.86	Medium
	Abuse as a whole		3.66	0.71	Medium

*Maximum degree (5)

Table (4) shows that the estimates of female university students for abuse as a whole came in a medium degree, where the mean was (3.66) .The field of verbal abuse ranked first with mean (3.92) and a standard deviation (0.78) and a high degree of appreciation, and the field of sexual abuse came second with mean (3.61) and a standard deviation (0.95) and medium degree, while the field of physical abuse ranked third and last with an average Arithmetic (3.46), standard deviation (0.86) and medium degree. Means and standard deviations of the responses of the female students were calculated on each item of each field of the study tool and related to the type of abuse experienced by the university students.

1. Field of verbal abuse:

Table 5: Means and standard deviations of the responses of female students on each items of the field tool (verbal abuse) in descending order according to the mean

Item No.	Field	Rank	Mean*	Standard deviation	Level
5	Telephone harassment	1	4.51	0.91	High
4	Embarrassment	2	4.42	0.82	High
1	Cursing	3	3.59	0.95	Medium
2	Contempt	4	3.58	0.97	Medium
3	Threaten	5	3.49	1.00	Medium
Verbal abuse			3.92	1.02	High

*Maximum degree (5)

Table (5) shows that the estimates of female students of verbal abuse came to a high degree, where the mean was (3.92) .item (4), which provides for "embarrassment", ranked second with mean of (4.42), standard deviation (0.82), and a degree of (0.91). A high estimate, while item (3), which provides for the "threaten" ranked last with mean (3.49) and a standard deviation (1.00) and medium estimate. As can be seen from the table, there are (2) verbal abuses out of (5) verbal abuses with a high (and) percentage rating (40%), and (3) verbal abuses out of (5) verbal abuses with a medium rating (medium), and a percentage (60%).

2. Field of physical abuse:

Table 6: Means and standard deviations of the responses of female students on each item of the field tool (physical abuse) in descending order according to the mean

Item No.	Field	Rank	Mean*	Standard deviation	Level
4	Body contact	1	3.79	1.21	High
3	Catch you	2	3.74	1.17	High
1	Beating with hands	3	3.71	1.09	High
9	Beating with a tool	4	3.67	0.99	High
5	Pulling hair	5	3.63	0.95	Medium
2	kick	6	3.59	0.89	Medium
6	Chucking to the ground	7	3.52	0.82	Medium
8	Snapping	8	3.49	0.79	Medium
7	strangulation	9	3.38	0.80	Medium
Physical abuse			3.61	0.93	Medium

*Maximum degree (5)

Table (6) shows that the estimates of female university students for physical abuse came in a medium degree, where the mean was 3.61.item (4), which is states " body contact" ranked first with a mean (3.79) and standard deviation (1.21) and a high degree, and item (3), which states that "catching you" second place with mean (3.74) and standard deviation (1.17) with a high degree, while item (7) which states that "strangulation" ranked last with mean (3.38) and a standard deviation (0.80) and a medium degree. As shown in the table, there are (4) physical abuses out of (9) that came with a high (and) percentage rating (44.4%), and (5) verbal abuses out of (9) physical abuses that came with an average rating (medium) and a percentage (55.6%).

3. Field of sexual abuse:

Table 7: Means and standard deviations of the responses of female students on each item of the field tool (sexual abuse) in descending order according to the mean

Item No.	Field	Rank	Mean*	Standard deviation	Level
1	Sexual comments	1	3.60	0.97	Medium
2	Annoying sexual jokes	2	3.54	0.99	Medium
3	Sexual signal	3	3.39	0.85	Medium
4	Touch is undesirable	0.92	0.92	0.92	Medium
Sexual abuse			3.46	0.81	Medium

*Maximum degree (5)

Table (7) shows that the estimates of female university students for sexual abuse came in a medium degree, where the mean was (3.46) . Item (1) which states that "sexual comments" ranked first with an average of 3.60 and a standard deviation (0.97) and medium degree. Item (2) which states that "sexual jokes" came second with an average of (3.54) and a standard deviation (0.99). While item (3), which state that "sexual signal", came in third place with mean (3.39), standard deviation (0.85) and medium degree , while item(4), which states "touch undesirable," ranked the latter have mean (3.32), a standard deviation (0.92) and medium degree. As shown in the table, all four abuses were rated (medium) and percentage (100%).

The second question is: What are the sources of abuse experienced by female students of Irbid National University?

To answer this question were calculated means and standard deviations of the responses of female university students on each item of the sources of abuse experienced by female university students, as shown in table (8).

Table 8: Means and standard deviations of the responses of female students on each item of places where abuse can occur to female students in descending order according to the mean

Item No.	Field	Rank	Mean*	Standard deviation	Level
1	Body contact	1	3.71	0.87	High
5	Catch you	2	3.34	0.92	Medium
4	Beating with hands	3	3.01	0.99	Medium
8	Beating with a tool	4	2.32	1.01	Low
2	Pulling hair	5	3.29	1.09	Low
6	kick	6	2.26	1.10	Low
7	Chucking to the ground	7	2.20	1.13	Low
3	Snapping	8	2.18	1.14	Low

*Maximum degree (5)

Table (8) shows that item (1), which provides for "student" ranked first with an average of (3.71) and standard deviation (0.87) and an average grade, and paragraph (5), which provides for "driver" in second place with an average (3.34) with a standard deviation (0.92) and an average score, while paragraph (3) which provides for "faculty member" ranked last with an

arithmetic mean (2.18) and a standard deviation (1.14) and a low grade. As shown in the table, there is only one source of abuse out of (8) sources of abuse came with a rating (high) and percentage (12.5%), and (2) source out of (8) sources of abuse (medium) and percentage (5) sources out of (8) sources of abuse came with a rating of (low) and a percentage (62.5%).

Question 3: What are the places of abuse of students of Irbid National University?

To answer this question, means and standard deviations of the responses of female students were calculated on each item of places where abuse can occur to female students, as shown in table (9).

Table 9: Means and standard deviations of the responses of female students on each item of places where abuse can occur to university students in descending order according to the mean

Item No.	Field	Rank	Mean*	Standard deviation	Level
2	transports	1	4.37	0.94	High
3	Behind the colleges	2	4.17	0.99	High
1	The street	3	3.99	1.01	High
4	Under the trees	4	3.84	1.08	High
5	On the upper floors	5	3.73	1.09	High
6	In the hallways	6	3.70	1.10	High
7	Student gathering places	7	3.69	1.14	High

*Maximum degree (5)

Table (9) shows that item (2) which states " transports" ranked first with an average of (4.37) and standard deviation (0.94) and a high degree, and item (3), which states "behind the colleges" ranked second with an average (4.17) and standard deviation (0.99) and a high degree, while item (7), which is for "student gathering places" ranked last with an arithmetic mean (3.69) and standard deviation (1.14) and an average grade. The table also shows that all places of abuse (7) places of abuse were rated (high) and percentage (100%).

Question 4: Are there any statistically significant differences in the level of abuse attributed to the college variable (scientific, humanity) among female university students?

To find out if there were differences between colleges on the abuse scale, the (T-test) was used. Table (10) shows means and standard deviations and test results to determine differences between colleges.

Table 10: T-Test results for differences between the means of college on the abuse scale

Variable	Gender	Mean	Standard deviation	T-value	Possibility
College	Humanity	3.24	0.67	3.62-	*0.000
	Scientific	3.01	0.78		

0.0001>P*

Table (10) shows that there are statistically significant differences between the colleges on the scale of abuse (T = - 3.62; P <0.0001). It is clear from the table that the average of human faculties (M = 3.24) are higher than the average scientific (M = 3.01).

Question 5: Are there any statistically significant differences in the level of abuse due to the GPA among female university students?

To find out whether there were differences between the GPA on the abuse scale, the (Kruskal-Wallis Test) was used for the differences in abuse due to the GPA variable, as shown in Table (11).

Table 11: Kruskal-Wallis Test Results for the differences in abuse were attributed to the GPA

Dependent variable	Means of GPA				Chi Square	Asymp. Sig
	Less than 67.9	68-75.9	76-83.9	84 and more		
Abuse	251.4	249.7	238.5	281.3	2.92	0.548

It is noted from Table (11) that the value of the test is (2.) with a level of significance equal to (0.548) which is more than (0.05), which indicates that there are no differences in the degrees of female students on the scale of abuse at the level of significance (0.05) due to the GPA mean.

Question 6: Are there any statistically significant differences in the level of abuse attributed to the variable of the academic year among female university students?

To determine if there were differences between the academic years on the abuse scale, the (ANOVA) test was used for the differences in abuse attributable to the academic year, as shown in Table (12).

Table 12: ANOVA Test results for the differences in the level of abuse are attributable to the academic year

Source of variance	Fd	Mean squares (MS)	Sum of squares(ss)	F Calculated	Sig
Between Groups	3	7.425	2.475	7.684	0.000
Within Groups	914	581.294	0.636		
Total	917	588.719	-		

Table (12) shows that there are statistically significant differences at the level ($\alpha = 0.05$) in the degree of abuse attributed to the academic year. To find the degree of these differences were used (Tukey Test) for two-dimensional comparisons of differences in the degree of abuse due to the variable of the academic year, as shown in Table (13).

Table 13: the results of the Tukey Test for post-twofold comparisons for the differences in degree of abuse are attributable to the academic year

Comparison	first	second	Third	Fourth
First	---	0.0132 -	0.0674 -	0.0849 -
second	---	---	0.0598 -	0.1154 *
Third	---	---	---	0.1268 *
Fourth	---	---	---	---

The post-twofold comparisons in Table (13) indicate that the differences in the degree of abuse attributable to the academic year were between the students of the second and third year on the one hand, and the students of the fourth year on the other hand, and for the benefit of the students of the second and third year, where the degree of abuse was the highest thing. Third

year students with an average (3.98), followed by students in the second year (3.81), students of the first year (3.79), and finally students of the fourth year with an average of (3.61), as shown in table (14).

Table 14: Numbers, means and standard deviations for the degree of abuse is attributable to the academic year

Academic year	No.	Mean	Standard deviation
Firstly	227	3.79	0.75
secondly	219	3.81	0.84
Third	238	3.98	0.72
Fourth	234	3.61	0.68

The results of the study indicated that **verbal abuse** is the most form of abuse experienced by female university students, and ranked first among other types of abuses included in the tool. This result can be attributed to the fact that verbal abuse is the most common and used in societies and the most serious mental health, because Most human behavior is verbal and students' exposure to verbal abuse as children may increase the likelihood of others being abused, because they have become the target of further harm due to low self-esteem, and abuse of any kind begins with insult and cursing, and is in the form of adjective Lewd in front of others, and because there is coeducational education in universities, Cultural, social, and economic differences may have led to ethical problems, as a result of finery, sorority, dysfunction, weak religious motivation, and social non-adaptation. Adolescents, and the weakness of religious motivation, and openness to cultural variables, may have pushed the youth to a conflict between desire and tradition, making them unstable troubled, and face many problems, and because of the large numbers of students within the university, it is Because of the presence of male and female students at this age in a mixed atmosphere may have helped to tempt the other party, because our society is going through a rapid phase of development, which in turn may affect children, especially the university youth. The results of this study are consistent with the study (Philpart, et al., 2009) which indicated the existence of the practice of physical and sexual abuse among students, and the Friday study (2009), which indicated that verbal abuse is the most common. The outcome of this study differs from that of Majali (2009) which indicated a low level of sexual abuse.

As for the field of **verbal abuse**, the results indicate that the item "telephone harassment" came first, and is the most prevalent among university students. This result may be attributed to civilizational progress and the entry of the world of communication, technology and globalization, Because of the presence of cell phones with the vast majority of students, mixing between the gender within the university, and the lack of adequate commitment in some students to lectures, and the preoccupation of each party with the other, may have led to the problems between genders. The "threat" item came last, and this result may be due to the presence of administrative control such as university security, which in turn reduces the development of abuse among students and tries to resolve it easily. The result of this study is consistent with the study (Ferns & Meerabeau, 2008) which indicated a significant occurrence of verbal abuse.

In the field of **physical abuse**, the results indicate that the "contact with the body" came first and this result may be due to the presence of large numbers of students in a simple space, which leads to contact with each other during the transition between lectures, or during registration and payment of university fees, or traffic jams. In the field of sexual abuse, the results indicate that the item "sexual comments" came first, and may be the reason for the female students' excessive interest in their personal appearance such as clothing, hair color, and beauty care, which caused them to sexual comments. The results of this study are consistent with the study (Bronner, et al, 2003) which indicated that (90%) of students are exposed to at least one type of sexual abuse.

while the item which states "undesirable touch" came in last place, and this indicates a low degree of undesirable touch, and may be explained in the light of the fact that the Jordanian society is a conservative Islamic and Eastern society, calls for adherence to the morality of virtue, and non-aggression on others, The results of this study differ with the results of the study Bronner et al. (2003), which indicated that the percentage of undesirable touch in nurses students by (33%), due to the nature of work and mixing female nurses and female nursing students, which helped to sexual harassment.

The results indicate that the "student" item came in first place for the sources of abuse among university female students. This may be attributed to the high number of students at the university, the mixing between them, and the weakness of their religious motivation, which caused all kinds of abuse, the nature of the age, deprivation, temptation, in addition to social and emotional changes, and the collision of achieving their ambitions and aspirations with the reality of their lives at the university and outside, And full of the pressure they realize they are trying to dump their pent-up feelings towards the students. The result of this study is consistent with the results of the Juma (2009) study which indicated that the student is the most abusive source.

While the item which states that "faculty members" came in last place, that is, the decrease in the source of abuse from faculty members, and the researchers may attribute this to the positive role played by faculty in guiding students and make them aware of what is best for them, and awareness of the laws and regulations of the university In addition to listening to their advice and suggestions, holding important courses and seminars and conferences centered on students, in order to reduce the gap between students and university professor, and increase the language of civilized dialogue between them.

The results indicate that the "transport" came first in places where abuse occurs, which means that the most places where abuse occurs are means of transport, and perhaps this result can be attributed to the only way through which students arrive to and from The university, and sometimes the student rides in more than one means of transport to reach the university and perhaps because of the congestion on transportation, increased exposure of female students to abuse, and may sometimes require students to sit next to students in the bus, which provides the opportunity to abuse female students with ease. This result is consistent with the results of the study of Obadah and Abu Doh (2007), which showed that the means of transport is one of the most places where abuse occurs to female university students (27.3%).

While the “student gathering places” section came last, perhaps due to the large number of students in one place, and the spread of university security in crowded places, it is difficult for students to abuse and harass them. The result of this study is consistent with the findings of the Juma (2009) study which indicated that the most frequent places of abuse are transportation.

Humanitarian faculty female students may be more likely to be subjected to abuse than female students from the scientific faculty, but they spend more time on campus with students because of the low level of difficulty of materials and assignments, which provides them with a large leisure time, which encourages abuse, humanitarian faculty students may be more likely to be subjected to abuse than female students from the scientific faculty, but they spend more time on campus with students because of the low level of difficulty of materials and assignments, which provides them with a large leisure time, which encourages abuse, and perhaps the ignorance of female students in university sanctions reinforced the commission of this behavior. The results of this study differ with the results of the Juma (2009) study which indicated that the absence of differences due to the impact of the faculty. The absence of differences in the GPA may be due to the similarity of conditions, pressures, problems and the university environment, and it seems that the abuse of them was not significantly affected by the GPA of female students, especially as the conditions and the university environment are similar for all female students regardless of their GPA. While the results indicated differences in the level of abuse for the variable of the academic year and for the second and third year, This result may be attributed to the fact that second and third year students are trying to adapt and build friendship, which has caused them some pressure to be more abusive than fourth-year students who have become more mature and thoughtful than reflected in the level of interaction with their classmates, and may begin to feel responsible for the GPA and the need for job, Which caused differences in the degree of abuse. The result of this study differs from that of Majali (2009) which indicated that there were no differences in the academic level.

5. RECOMMENDATIONS

In light of the results of the study, the researchers recommend the following:

1. Work to increase the complementary programs of the curriculum within the university, to engage students with what is useful.
2. Provide guidance bulletins at the beginning of each semester, especially for new students, explaining the factors causing abuse and violence within the university, and explain the laws and penalties for violators, and introduce students to places and guidance centers within the university.
3. Conduct research and studies related to university students and interest in solving the problems facing them.

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